

Gender assignment in disorders of sex: An Islamic perspective from Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Genital ambiguity, is defined as a group of congenital conditions in which development of chromosomal, gonadal, or anatomic sex is atypical. It constitutes a major social emergency and the decision making in relation to sex assignment has been perceived as an extremely disturbing and difficult to both families and health care professionals. It can also be a medical emergency as it may lead to life-threatening adrenal crisis. Each patient should be evaluated individually by a well-coordinated experienced multidisciplinary team of specialists in a higher center capable of managing such disorders. The team should include a geneticist, neonatologist, endocrinologist, pediatric surgeon, urologist, psychiatrist and psychologist, a social worker, and other specialists such as a nurse, and gynecologist to be consulted whenever needed.

The estimated incidence was found to be approximately 0.1% to 0.2% worldwide i.e, 1:4500-5000 live birth. The 46XX is the most common cause, while the majority of these patients congenital adrenal hyperplasia (CAH) is the most underlying aetiology. The 46XY DSD is a heterogeneous disorders that often result from a disruption in the production or response to testosterone, dihydrotestosterone, or Mullerian inhibitory substances. Chromosomal DSD includes condition resulting from abnormal meiosis, including Klinefelter syndrome (47XXY) and Turner syndrome.

The evaluation of patients with sex disorders requires a thorough history, physical examination, karyotype, serum electrolytes, and specific hormones, such as 17-OH-progesterone. The pediatric radiologist has a major role in diagnosis.

In Saudi Arabia, a general guidelines were suggested by the council of senior ulama to manage patients with DSD in accordance with the islamic laws. This should be the practice in other muslim countries. Health professionals need to be aware of the existence of such recommendation for a better care of patients.

Keywords: Genital; Ambiguity; Islamic perceptive; Gender; Assignment; Multidisciplinary team

1. Introduction

Genital ambiguity (uncertain or atypical genitalia) represents a wide range of congenital conditions in which the chromosomal, gonadal or anatomic sex is atypical. It constituted a major complex social and medical emergency that requires prompt response by a well-coordinated multidisciplinary team of specialists. Several conditions produce significant salt loss which, if unrecognized, and early treated may lead to shock and even death. The team should include a geneticist, neonatologist, endocrinologist, pediatric surgeon, urologist, psychiatrist and psychologist, a social worker, and other specialists such as a nurse, and gynecologist to be consulted whenever needed (1-11).

Limited data are available on the exact incidence of DSD with genital ambiguity at birth, which has been estimated to be approximately 0.1% to 0.2% world-wide, i.e, 1 in 4500-5000 live births. Thyen and associate (12) reported from

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Germany that ambiguous genitalia incidence was four-fold higher in infants of non-German origin compared with the general population. This was attributed to an increase in autosomal recessive forms of disorders of sex due to higher rates of consanguinity in migrant population. In support to this the higher incidence of genital ambiguity in Saudi Arabia where the consanguinity rate is high (8,13), the incidence of ambiguous genitalia was reported as 1 in 2500 live-births (14-16). Likewise that of 1 in 3000 live births in Egypt (17). Rate of disorders of sex is even higher in some other countries like, Turkey. Where Aydin and associates (18) have reported higher incidence of 1.3 in 1000 live births.

In 2006, the Lawson Wilkins Pediatric Endocrine Society (LWPES) and the European society for Pediatric Endocrinology (ESPE) published a consensus statement of intersex disorders and proposed the umbrella term disorders of sex development “DSD” instead of terms like “intersex”, pseudo hermaphroditism (PH), “hermaphroditism” “ sex reversal “, which are often perceived as pejorative by patients and can be confusing to both health professionals and parents. This was modified later (19-21). Congenital adrenal hyperplasia (CAH) is the most common cause for DSD in the newborn world-wide. Other notable causes include partial androgen insensitivity syndrome (PIAS). Unfortunately, a great number of cases do not have an identifiable causes, particularly among 46XY DSD, which highlight the great importance of an experienced team with multidisciplinary focus. Congenital malformations can also cause disorders of sex development (DSD), many of which have a primary genetic cause, and others which have a more structural or developmental causes and do not have any hormonal causes. These include VATER/VACTER associations or cloacal exstrophy.

The main objective of this article is to outline the clinical approach to the management of patients with disorders of sex. Gender related issues from the perspective of the islamic jurisprudence are also highlighted and discussed.

2. The practical approach of diagnosis of disorders of sex development “DSD”

The management of patients with genital ambiguity and disorders of sex should be managed in a highly specialized medical center, where a multi-disciplinary team of specialists capable of managing such disorder is present. A thorough history and physical examination were essential. Special hormonal investigations and serum electrolytes can identify the etiology. Establishing the genetic sex (karyotype) should be the first step in the management (25-27)

The pediatric Radiologist has a major role in determining the internal anatomical structures. Abdominal ultrasonography remains the first choice. (Figure 1), this could include genitography, (figure 2), and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), (figure 3). (28-32).

Figure 1 Ultrasound pelvis demonstrates presence of the uterus (white arrow). The urinary bladder (white star)

Figure 2 Fluoroscopy genitogram demonstrates normal appearing urinary bladder (black star) and urethra (white arrow) with dilated upper vagina (black arrowhead) with communication with lower urethra (black arrow)

Figure 3 (A and B) MRI pelvis T2 weighted image sagittal (A) and axial (B) demonstrates presence of a dilated upper vagina (black star) and the uterus (white arrow) with two separate cavities (white arrow heads) (bicornute uterus).
No ovaries or testes were visualized

The following represents the diagnostic algorithm for patients in which the gonads are either palpable or not (figure 4). However, decision making algorithms based on the karyotype, and other hormonal investigations were available (27, 33). Special procedures like laparoscopy or Laparotomy with gonadal biopsies might be needed at times. However, a biopsy as well as laparoscopy is not required when the diagnosis is clearly established biochemically or by gene studies. (34)

Figure 4 Diagnostic Algorithm for patients with ambiguous genitalia, based on gonadal palpation

3. Discussion on issues related to ambiguity of genitalia

Management of patient with DSD is undoubtedly complex and challenging. Biomedical, psychological, cultural and religious factors, among others, seems to be influential (14,35-38). Kuhnle and Krahl (39) demonstrates earlier the impact of culture on sex assignment and gender development in patients with disorders of sex. This was in accordance with Meyer-Bahlburg (40). Although several studies from different Muslim countries like Saudi Arabia, Egypt and Turkey which indicated preference of male sex despite of the gonadal makeup and karyotype (41-43). Also Warne and Raza have reported that In India and Pakistan children with disorders of sex are more likely to be raised as males.(44) Nevertheless, not all countries have preferences for male sex as stated by Zainuddin and Mahdy from Malaysia (45).

Great need for a better psychological support, to encourage self-acceptance, and counseling for individuals with DSD and their parents. It is always considered as a difficult task that requires a skillful personals. It should be clear, frank and honest. (51-54) The need for encounter and exchange ideas with other parents with similar experience with DSD are found to be helpful. Furthermore, there is a need for a continuous physiological support and counseling. Efforts should be made to improve strategies and quality of counseling. Incorporating a religious scholar with good understanding of genital ambiguity into the multidisciplinary team will ease the discussion with patients and their family. Finally, in each country establishing a central body called " Gender assignment council " to ensure a better control. Their contact telephone number and E-mail should be available to facilitate communication.

Furthermore, patient and or family should be fully informed of the condition and the possible outcome including surgical procedures (55-61). This will improve decision making and acceptance.

In Saudi Arabia the council of senior Ulama, the highest religious authority in the country, suggested a set of guidelines to manage patients with DSD. (62-64)

There is an impression fostered by the local clinical experience as published earlier (14,47) That these guidelines are practical and easy to apply Zabidi (65) has reviewed the issues related to genital ambiguity from both the Islamic and medical perspectives. Management of patients with DSD and genital ambiguity continues to be challenging and complex. To find a solution for all the issues from one Islamic council seems to be insufficient. Certainly, there is a need to bridge the gap between the medical professionals and Islamic scholars around the world. Guidelines for gender assignment and issue related to the decision-making process require in-depth research.

4. Conclusion

The management of patients with genital ambiguity is challenging and complex. There is an urgent need to establish unified general guidelines to manage patients with genital ambiguity. A combined efforts between the council of senior Ulama of Saudi Arabia and the International Islamic Fiqh Academy of the muslim world league should be encouraged. Furthermore, counseling strategies and psychological support need to be improved in quality. Exchange with other patients, or parents with DSD with similar experience has been of importance. In addition, further studies on the subject should be executed. Finally, to ensure a better care, health professionals need to be aware of the existing guidelines.

Compliance with ethical standards

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References

- [1] Saenger PH. Physiology of sexual determination and differentiation In: Brook CGD and Hindmarsh PC, eds. Clinical Pediatric Endocrinology 4th edn. Oxford (UK) Blackwell Scientific Publisher 2001;60-76.
- [2] Rappaport R, Forest MG. Disorders of sexual differentiation. In: Bertrand J, Rappaport R, Sizomenko PC, editors. Paediatric endocrinology: physiology, pathophysiology, and clinical aspects. 2nd ed. London (GB): Williams and Wilkins; 1993. pp. 447-470.
- [3] Sperling M. Pediatric Endocrinology. 4th ed. Philadelphia Pennsylvania Saunders, Elsevier 2014.
- [4] Lee PA. A perspective on the approach to the intersex child born with genital ambiguity. J Pediatr Endocrinol Metab. 2004; 17:133-140.
- [5] Aaronson IA, Aaronson AJ. How should we classify intersex disorders? J Pediatr Urol. 2010; 6:443-446.
- [6] Hiort O, Birnbaum W, Marshall L, Wunsch L, Werner R, et al. Management of disorders of sex development. Nat Rev Endocrinol. 2014;10: 520-529.
- [7] Houk CP, Lee PA Update on disorders of sex development. Current Opinion in Endocrinology, Diabetes and Obesity. 2012;19: 28-32.
- [8] AL Swailem MM, AL Zahrani OS, AL Ghofaili L, Qasem E, AL Mohanaa M, AL Sagheir A, et al, Molecular genetics and phenotype/genotype correlation of 5- α reductase deficiency in a highly consanguineous population, 2019: 63:361-368.
- [9] Wherrett DK Approach to the Infant with a Suspected Disorder of Sex Development. Pediatr Clin North Am. 2015; 62: 983-999.
- [10] van Zoest M, Bijker EM, Kortmann BBM, Kempers M, van Herwaarden AE et al. Sex Assignment and Diagnostics in Infants with Ambiguous Genitalia - A Single-Center Retrospective Study. Sex Dev. 2019; 13:109-117.
- [11] Chavhan GB, Parra DA, Oudjhane K, Miller SF, Babyn PS, Pippi Salle FL. Imaging of ambiguous genitalia: classification and diagnostic approach. Radiographics. 2008; 28:1891-904.
- [12] Thyen U, Lanz K, Holterhus PM, Hiort O. Epidemiology and initial management of ambiguous genitalia at birth in Germany. Horm Res. 2006;66:195-203.
- [13] Al Jurayyan NA, Osman H. The increased prevalence of congenital adrenal hyperplasia in Saudi Arabia: the role of consanguinity and multiple siblings involvement. Eur J Res Med Sci 2015; 3(11) 31-34

- [14] Abdullah MA, Katugampola M, al-Habib S, al-Jurayyan N, al-Samarrai A, Al-Nuaim A, Patel PJ, Niazi M. Ambiguous genitalia: medical, socio-cultural and religious factors affecting management in Saudi Arabia. *Ann Trop Paediatr.* 1991;11:343-8.
- [15] ALAgha AE, Thomsett MJ, Batch JA. The child of uncertain sex: 17 years of experience. *J Pediatr Child Health.* 2001;37:348-351.
- [16] Al Jurayyan NA. Disorders of sex development: diagnostic approaches and management options-an islamic perspective. *Malays J Med Sci.* 2011 Jul;18:4-12.
- [17] Mazen I, Hiort O, Bassiouny R, El Gammal M. Differential diagnosis of disorders of sex development in Egypt. *Horm Res.* 2008;70:118-23.
- [18] Aydin BK, Saka N, Bas F, Bas EK, Coban A, Yildirim S, Guran T, Darendeliler F. Frequency of Ambiguous Genitalia in 14,177 Newborns in Turkey. *J Endocr Soc.* 2019;24;3:1185-1195.
- [19] Lee PA, Nordenström A, Houk CP, Ahmed SF, Auchus R, Baratz A et al. Global DSD Update Consortium. Global Disorders of Sex Development Update since 2006: Perceptions, Approach and Care. *Horm Res Paediatr.* 2016;85:158-180.
- [20] Hughes IA, Nihoul-Fékété C, Thomas B, Cohen-Kettenis PT. Consequences of the ESPE/LWPES guidelines for diagnosis and treatment of disorders of sex development. *Best Pract Res Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2007;21:351-365.
- [21] Ahmed SF, Achermann J, Alderson J, Crouch NS, Elford S, Hughes IA et al. Society for Endocrinology UK Guidance on the initial evaluation of a suspected difference or disorder of sex development (Revised 2021). *Clin Endocrinol.* 2021; 95:818-840.
- [22] Shamma RA, Atef S, Arafa N. Etiological classification and clinical spectrum of Egyptian pediatric patients with disorder of sex development, single center experience. *Endokrynol Pol.* 2021;72:558-565
- [23] Morel Y, Rey R, Teinturier C, Nicolino M, Michel-Calemard L, Mowszowicz I et al. Aetiological diagnosis of male sex ambiguity: a collaborative study. *Eur J Pediatr.* 2002 Jan;161:49-59.
- [24] Erdoğan S, Kara C, Uçaktürk A, Aydın M. Etiological classification and clinical assessment of children and adolescents with disorders of sex development. *J Clin Res Pediatr Endocrinol.* 2011;3:77-83.
- [25] Krishnan S, Meyer J, Khattab A. Ambiguous Genitalia in the Newborn. [Updated Dec 2,2019]. In: Feingold KR, Anawalt B, Boyce A, et al., editors. *Endotext* [Internet]. South Dartmouth (MA): MDTText.com, Inc.; 2000-2022.
- [26] Diaz A, Lipman-Diaz EG. Disorders of Sex Development. *Pediatr Rev* 2021;42: 414–426.
- [27] ALOmran H, ALJurayyan N. Disorders of Sex Development (DSD): Diagnostic Approach and Management in Infants and Children. *Biomed J Sci Tech Res.* 2021; 36:28940-50.
- [28] ALJurayyan RN, ALJurayyan ArN, ALOmran HI, ALJurayyan NA. Diagnostic Imaging of Disorders of Sex Development (DSD) in Infants and Children. *Int J Sci Res.* 2022;11:24-27:doi10.36106ijsr
- [29] Kanemoto K, Hayashi Y, Kojima Y, Maruyama T, Ito M, et al. Accuracy of Ultrasonography and Magnetic Resonance Imaging in the Diagnosis of non-palpable testis. *Int J Urol.* 2005;12: 668-672
- [30] Riccabona M, Darge K, Lobo ML et al ESPR Uroradiology Taskforce - imaging recommendations in paediatric uroradiology, part VIII: retrograde urethrography, imaging disorder of sexual development and imaging childhood testicular torsion. *Pediatr Radiol.* 2015;45:2023-2028
- [31] Mansour SM, Hamed ST, Adel L, Kamal RM, Ahmed DM, et al. Does MRI add to ultrasound in the assessment of disorders of sex development? *Eur J Radiol.* 2012;81(9): 2403-2410.
- [32] Al Jurayyan NA, Patel PJ, al Herbish AS, Abdullah MA, Abo-Bakr AM, et al. Ambiguous genitalia: comparative role of pelvic ultrasonography and genitography. *Ann Trop Paediatr.* 1995; 15(3): 203-207
- [33] León NY, Reyes AP, Harley VR. A clinical algorithm to diagnose differences of sex development. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol.* 2019;7:560-574.
- [34] Hutson JM, Kimber C. Laparoscopy for DSD. In: Hutson J, Warne G, Grover S (ed). *Disorders of sex development.* Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. 2012; <http://doi.org/10.107/978-3-642-229640-18>.
- [35] Subchi I, Latifa R, Hartati N, Nahartini D, Yuliani A, Roup M. The Influence of Religiosity, Cultural Values, and Marital Commitment to Infidelity in Marital Life. *J Crit Rev* 2019,6:50-58

- [36] ESHRE Capri Working Group. The influence of social factors on gender health. *Hum Reprod.* 2016;31:1631-1637.
- [37] Uslu R, Oztop D, Ozcan O, Yilmaz S, Berberoğlu M, Adiyaman P et al. Factors contributing to sex assignment and reassignment decisions in Turkish children with 46,XY disorders of sex development. *J Pediatr Endocrinol Metab.* 2007;20:1001-1015.
- [38] Weidler EM, Peterson KE. The impact of culture on disclosure in differences of sex development. *Semin Pediatr Surg.* 2019;28:150840.
- [39] Kuhnle U, Krahl W. The impact of culture on sex assignment and gender development in intersex patients. *Perspect Biol Med.* 2002;45:85-103.
- [40] Meyer-Bahlburg, H.F.L.. Gender and sexuality in classic congenital adrenal hyperplasia. *Endocrinology Metabolism Clinics of North America*,2001; 30, 155-171
- [41] Taha SA. Male pseudohermaphroditism: factors determining the gender of rearing in Saudi Arabia. *Urology.* 1994;43:370-374.
- [42] Dessouky N. GENDER ASSIGNMENT FOR CHILDREN WITH INTERSEX PROBLEMS: AN EGYPTIAN PERSPECTIVE. *Egyptian Journal of Surgery.* 2001,20:499-515
- [43] Ozbey H. Gender assignment in female congenital adrenal hyperplasia: a difficult experience. *BJU International.* 2004;94,388-391
- [44] Warne GL, Raza J. Disorders of sex development (DSDs), their presentation and management in different cultures. *Rev Endocr Metab Disord.* 2008;9:227-236.
- [45] Zainuddin AA, Mahdy ZA. The Islamic Perspectives of Gender-Related Issues in the Management of Patients With Disorders of Sex Development. *Arch Sex Behav.* 2017;46:353-360.
- [46] Abdullah MA, Saeed U, Abass A, Lubna K, Weam A, Ali AS, Elmwla IF. Disorders of sex development among Sudanese children: 5-year experience of a pediatric endocrinology clinic. *J Pediatr Endocrinol Metab.* 2012;25:1065-72.
- [47] AlJurayyan NA. Ambiguous genitalia: two decades of experience. *Ann Saudi Med.*2011;31:284-8
- [48] Nabil MD. GENDER ASSIGNMENT FOR CHILDREN WITH INTERSEX PROBLEMS: AN EGYPTIAN PERSPECTIVE. *Egypt J Surg;*2001, 20:499-515.
- [49] Tiryaki S, Tekin A, Yagmur İ, Özen S, Özbaran B, Gökşen D et al. Parental Perception of Terminology of Disorders of Sex Development in Western Turkey. *J Clin Res Pediatr Endocrinol.*2018 31;10:216-222.
- [50] Mansoor J, Aftab S, Yaqoop M. Ambiguous genitalia: An overview of 7 years experience at the Children's Hospital & Institute of Child Health, Lahore, Pakistan. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2019,35:151-155
- [51] Cohen-Kettenis P. Psychological long-term outcome in intersex conditions. *Horm Res.* 2005;64:2:27-30.
- [52] Slijper FM, Drop SL et al. Long-term psychological evaluation of intersex children. *Arch Sex Behav.* 1998;27:125-144.
- [53] Liao L, Roen K. The role of psychologists in multi-disciplinary teams for intersex/diverse sex development: interviews with British and Swedish clinical specialists. *Psychology and sexuality* 2021,21:202-216.
- [54] Lampalzer U, Briken P, Schweizer K. Psychosocial care and support in the field of intersex/diverse sex development (dsd): counselling experiences, localisation and needed improvements. *Int J Impot Res.* 2021;33(2):228-242
- [55] Michala L, Liao L-M, Wood D, Conway GS, Creighton SM. Practice changes in childhood surgery for ambiguous genitalia? *J Pediatr Urol* 2014;10:934-9.
- [56] Mouriquand P.D.E. Mure P.Y. Current concepts in hypospadiology *BJU Int* 2004,93:26-34.
- [57] Eroglu E. Tekant G. Gundogdu G. Emir H. Ercan O. Soyletet Y. Feminizing surgical management of intersex patients *Pediatr Surg Int* 2004,20:543-7.
- [58] Burgu B. Duffy P.G. Cuckow P. Ransley P. Wilcox D.T. Long-term outcome of vaginal reconstruction: comparing techniques and timing. *J Pediatr Uro* 2007,31:316-20.
- [59] Callens N, Hoebeke P. Phalloplasty: a panacea for 46,XY disorder of sex development conditions with penile deficiency? *Endocr Dev* 2014;27:222-33.

- [60] Mouriquand P, Caldamone A, Malone P, Frank JD, Hoebeke P. The ESPU/SPU standpoint on the surgical management of Disorders of Sex Development (DSD). *J Pediatr Urol* 2014; 10:8-10.
- [61] Kutney K, Konczal L, Kaminski B, Uli N. Challenges in the diagnosis and management of disorders of sex development, *Birth Defects Research*, 2016,108: 293-308.
- [62] Consensus statement on intersex issues: No 176. The Senior Ulama Council; 1992.
- [63] Al Herbish AS, Al Jurayyan NA, Abo Bakr AM, Abdullah MA, Al Hussain M, Al Rabeah AA, et al.; Sex-reassignment: A challenging problem Current medical and Islamic guidelines. *Ann Saudi Mod.* 1996, 16(1) 12-15.
- [64] Al Jurayyan NA; sex assignment and reassignment: a pediatric endocrinologist perspective; more than three decades of experience *sch J App Med Sci* 2015;3:2024-2032.
- [65] Zabidi T. Analytical Review of Contemporary Fatwas in Resolving Biomedical Issues Over Gender Ambiguity. *J Relig Health* 2019,58:153-167